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Effect of different concentrations of aqueous crude neem seed oil extract on root knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* species) infecting okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) in Ishiagu, Nigeria

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Abstract

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This experiment investigated the effects of different concentrations of aqueous crude neem seed oil extract on root-knot nematode (*Meloidogyne* species) infesting okra in Ishiagu, at the Research and Teaching Farm of the Federal College of Agriculture, Ishiagu, Ebonyi State, Nigeria, during the 2024 and 2025 cropping seasons. The experimental design used was Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with five (5) treatments replicated three (3) times. The treatments used were aqueous crude neem seed oil extract at 100 ml diluted with 1, 2, and 3 liters of water, positive control (Worm Force, an inorganic nematicide at 20 g/m²) and a control (negative control). Data were collected on plant height, number of leaves, number and weight of fruit, number of galled roots, and galls per root (root index). Data collected were averaged over the two years and analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA). Significant treatment means were separated using the least significant difference (LSD), and all inferences were made at a 5% level of probability. The result showed that 100 ml/3L aqueous crude neem seed oil extract significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced okra yield and reduced the incidence of root-knot nematode (*Meloidogyne* species) infections on okra in Ishiagu. Okra farmers in Ishiagu are therefore advised to grow the crop using aqueous crude neem seed oil extract at 100 ml/3L of water to enhance growth and yield, with a concomitant reduction in nematode infections on okra.

Introduction

Okra, *Abelmoschus esculentus* L. (Moench), according to Amadi (2023), is an annual fruit vegetable crop belonging to the Malvaceae family. Okra is found in its wild state on the alluvial banks of the Nile, and the Egyptians were the first to cultivate it in the basin of the Nile. It was propagated then through North Africa to the

Mediterranean, the Balkans, and India. Okra is believed to have originated in Ethiopia or West Africa, where it was first cultivated thousands of years ago. From there, it spread throughout Africa and eventually made its way to the Middle East, India, and Southeast Asia (Swamy, 2023).

It is an economic crop and income-generating crop for rural farmers in the

eastern part of Nigeria due to the sale of its immature fresh and dried fruits, which are made into diverse soup products as well as other delicacies. Swamy (2023) noted that okra is an economically important vegetable crop grown in tropical and subtropical parts of the world and is suitable for cultivation as a garden crop as well as on large commercial farms. Oladejo (2014) noted that it is among the most important vegetable crops in Nigeria, contributing massively to the Nigerian diet as a main constituent of soup. Okra is rich in magnesium, folate, antioxidants, and vitamins C, K, and A, which can help support healthy pregnancy, heart health, and blood sugar and may even have anticancer properties (Swamy, 2023). According to Udoh *et al.* (2005), okra varieties vary by plant height, size of fruit, colour, early or late maturity, and they include white velvet, green velvet, long pod, lady finger, and dwarf green pods. Elkhalfa *et al.* (2021) opined that okra contributes to human nutrition by providing lipids, proteins, carbohydrates, minerals, and vitamins. It contributes an important part of the diet to many people in the tropics, more especially in the Southeast, Nigeria. Okra is essentially a tropical crop and among the most commonly grown vegetables throughout Nigeria (Nweke *et al.*, 2013).

The protein found in okra helps to build muscle tissue and helps to lower serum cholesterol, reducing the risk of heart disease. Okra is a good source of calcium, which helps to keep the recommended level of vitamin B6, and folic acid is present in half a cup of cooked okra. The vitamin is required for good vision, proper circulation of blood, bone growth, and normal bone strength and lessens the chance of fractures (Grubben and Denton, 2004). It is cultivated throughout the tropical and warm temperate regions of the

world for its fibrous fruits or pods containing round, white seeds. It is among the most heat and drought-tolerant vegetable species in the world and will tolerate soils with heavy clay and intermittent moisture, but frost can damage the pods. According to Ayeni *et al.* (2023), all parts of the okra plant are useful; its leaves and tender shoots can be cooked and eaten by humans and also eaten fresh by livestock like cattle, goats, sheep, etc.

Okra has been reported to face many challenges during production in the field, especially if it is attacked by different types of pests. Root-knot nematodes (RKN) are sedentary endoparasites feeding at one site on enlarged and modified cells and represent the most advanced and successful type of parasitism; they are biotrophic and induce profound changes in the roots of their host as they feed. Galls on roots, which can be up to 3.3 cm in diameter but are usually smaller; reduction in plant vigour; yellowing plants which wilt in hot weather. Plants infested with RKN include symptoms of chlorosis, wilting, galling of roots and tubers, stunted growth, root lesions and yield loss, and these signs are like those of nutrient deficiencies, in particular nitrogen deficiency (Osei *et al.*, 2011 and Nguyen *et al.*, 2018). Root galling is an apparent sign of *Meloidogyne* infection and can easily be diagnosed by farmers. The induced gall formed in the roots due to nematode infection eventually impedes normal uptake of water and nutrients, and it also facilitates the infection by some soil-borne phytopathogens, which may enter the xylem and disrupt the movement of water, thus causing extensive damage to the crop. However, there are some inorganic chemicals used in controlling nematodes in the soil, called nematicides. These can be fumigants, like chloropicrin or methyl bromide, or

nervous system toxins, such as carbamates and organophosphates. Fumigants are injected into the soil to kill nematodes, while nervous system toxins target the nematode's nervous system.

The nematicidal substances obtained from plants can be considered to be biodeteriorated by microorganisms, thereby resulting in decomposed products. In this case, fewer residues are expected to result from the use of these products (Aoudia *et al.*, 2012). Some medicinal plants are believed to have natural products in the form of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, quinone, tannins, saponins, sterols, and volatile essential oils. Plants' bioactive substances display various anti-pathogenic properties (Akhtar *et al.*, 2008). These phytochemicals showed nematicidal properties on plant parasitic nematodes (Khan *et al.*, 2017). In addition, plant natural products are easily biodegradable; therefore, they do not tend to pollute the environment (Akhtar *et al.*, 2008).

Neem is one of the most studied plants with components that have attracted global attention for their insecticidal, fungicidal, bactericidal, and nematocidal properties (Gajalakshmi and Abbasi, 2004). The seed and leaf extracts of neem were found to cause 100% juvenile mortality of the root-knot nematodes and some free-living nematodes (Upadhyay *et al.*, 2003).

Okra is one of the tropical vegetable crops that is highly attacked by root knot nematode, causing enormous yield and income losses to the farmers. Ishiagu farmers are experiencing such losses. Nematode control has been through the use of inorganic nematicides, which are costly and detrimental to both the farmer and the environment when applied. The problems of the currently used nematicides have raised the need to find

alternative, low-input, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly nematode strategies to alleviate the pest problem of root-knot nematodes.

The main objective of the study was to determine the effect of different concentrations of aqueous crude neem seed oil extract on root knot nematode (*Meloidogyne* species) infecting okra in Ishiagu.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental location/site description:

This experiment was conducted at the research and teaching farm of the Federal College of Agriculture, Ishiagu, Ebonyi State, during the 2024 and 2025 cropping seasons. Ishiagu is located at longitude 07⁰46¹E and latitude 05⁰45¹N with a mean annual temperature of 29 °C and a mean annual rainfall of about 1350 mm. The area lies within the derived savannah vegetation zone of Southeastern Nigeria, with grassland and shrub trees combined together. Two distinct seasons are reported: the dry season, from November to March, and the rainy season, from April to October (Nwite *et al.*, 2008).

2. Materials:

Seeds of the local Ishiagu okra variety, which is susceptible to root-knot nematode infections, were used for the experiment. The treatments (Neem seed) were sourced within the college environment, while the inorganic nematicide (Wormforce Oxamyl 3% GR, a contact systemic and stomach insecticide and nematicide, manufactured by Global Alliance for chemical industries LTD, KM1 Ibadan/Ijebu Ode Express way, Igbaro Area, Oyo State, Nigeria) was procured from the manufacturer.

The treatments used were 100 ml of aqueous crude neem seed oil extract diluted with one (1), two (2) and, three (3) liters of water, with a positive control (Worm Force, Inorganic nematicide at 20 g/m²) and a negative

control (No application). The experimental design used was a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with 5 (five) treatments replicated three (3) times. The experimental field size was 10 m by 10 m with a plot of 2m x 2m each.

3. Field preparation:

The experimental field was cleared, pegged, and laid out into three blocks. Native hoe was used in making the beds, which were measured 2m x 2m = 4 m² (net plot size).

4. Preparation of the treatments:

Two (2) kg of dried neem seeds were initially boiled with three (3) liters of tap water for 45 minutes at 100 °C and sieved to remove the fiber. The filtrate was further boiled for 60 minutes at 100 °C till all the water was evaporated, leaving the crude oil. 100ml/ of extract was diluted with 1, 2 and 3 liters of water, respectively, to form the treatments.

5. Planting:

Okra was sown at a spacing of 50 cm x 50 cm and at the rate of one seed per hole. This gave a total plant population

of one hundred and eighty plants (180) in the experimental field.

6. Application of treatments:

The treatments were randomly allocated to various plots. The treatments were applied two days before planting and one month after planting using a hand sprayer to minimize drift. While the inorganic nematicide was applied at 80 g per 4 m² plot.

7. Harvesting:

Harvesting was done by plucking the mature fruit from each plot. Each harvest was weighed using a sensitive scale, and the average was recorded.

8. Data collection:

Data were collected on the following parameters: plant height (cm) and number of leaves were obtained at 4, 6, and 8 weeks after planting (WAP), number and weight of fruits, number of galled roots, and galls per root were obtained at harvest. The number of galls per root was scaled according to Ogwulumba and Okonta (2015), as shown below in Table (1).

Table (1): The number of galls per root according to Ogwulumba and Okonta (2015).

Rating	Number of Galls/Root	Infection Level
0.	No galls	No infection
1.	1-10	Mild infection
2.	11-20	Moderate infection
3.	21-30	Moderately high infection
4.	31-40	High infection
5.	41-50	Very high infection
6.	>51	Severe infection

9. Data analysis:

Data collected was averaged over the two years and subjected to statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA), according to the procedure of Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Significant treatment means were separated using Fisher’s least significant difference (FLSD) at a 5% probability level as outlined in Obi (2002).

Results and discussion

The results in Table (2) showed that at 4 WAP, there was a significant (P <

0.05) effect by the treatments on the plant height. Crude neem seed oil at 100 ml/3 L recorded the highest mean height (8.7 cm), followed closely by the positive control plot (8.0 cm), while the lowest plant height (2.5cm) was observed in the negative control plot. At 6 and 8 WAP, indicating that there was no significant (P > 0.05) difference among the treatments in the plant height. The treatments were statistically the same.

Table (2): Effect of different levels of aqueous crude neem seed oil extract on plant heights after planting.

Treatment	4WAP	6WAP	8WAP
Neem oil at 100ml/1 L of water	4.4	15.8	18.2
Neem oil at 100ML/2L of water	7.96	13.6	16.2
Neem oil at 100ML/3L of water	8.7	18.0	20.9
Worm Force at 20g/m ² (Positive control)	8.0	14.2	16.9
Negative Control	2.5	10.5	12.0
LSD (0.05)	2.1	NS	NS

NS = Not significant

On the number of leaves, at 4, 6 and 8 weeks after planting (4 WAP), there

was no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference amongst the treatments (Table 3).

Table (3): Effect of different concentrations of aqueous crude neem seed oil extract on number of leaves at 4, 6 and 8 weeks after planting.

Treatment	4WAP	6WAP	8WAP
Neem oil at 100ml/1l of water	4.1	5.0	4.1
Neem oil at 100ml/2 l of water	4.3	4.8	4.0
Neem oil at 100ml/3 l of water	4.5	6.1	7.0
Worm Force at 20g/m ² (Positive control)	4.3	5.6	5.2
Negative Control	2.6	3.2	3.5
LSD (0.05)	NS	NS	NS

NS = Not Significant

The results in Table (4) showed that the treatments significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced the production and number of fruits at harvest. The highest number of fruits was obtained from the plots treated with neem oil at 100 ml / 3 L, which gave (43.7), followed by the positive control, which recorded (25.7), while the lowest number of fruits (15.7) was observed in negative control plot.

The fruit weight was significantly affected ($P < 0.05$) by the treatments. The highest fruit weight (3.71 t/ha) was recorded under the Neem oil at 100 ml / 3L treated plot, followed by the positive control plot, which gave (2.61 t/ha), while the lowest weight of fruits at harvest (1.07 t/ha) was obtained in the negative control plot.

Table (4): Effect of different concentrations of aqueous crude neem seed oil extract on number and weight of fruits at harvest.

Treatment	Number of fruits	Weight of fruits (t/h)
Neem oil at 100ml/1 L of Water	17.7	1.51
Neem oil at 100ML/2 L of water	28.0	2.08
Neem oil at 100ml/3L of water	43.7	3.71
Worm Force at 20 g/m ² (Positive control)	25.7	2.61
Negative Control	15.7	1.07
LSD (0.05)	9.1	1.21

The results in Table (5) showed that the treatments significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected the number of galled roots observed at harvest. The lowest gall incidence (0.6) occurred at the plots treated with neem oil at 100 ml / 1 L, followed by worm force (positive control), which recorded (1.8), while the negative control recorded the highest (5.38) number of galls per plant. The

result also showed that treatments used significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced the occurrence of galls per root, as recorded in Table (5). The number of galls per root was highest at the negative control, while other treatments recorded similar lowest gall indices. The number of galls per root at the negative control was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than at other treatment levels.

Table (5): Effect of different concentrations of aqueous crude neem seed oil extract on the number of galled roots and galls per root at harvest.

Treatment	Number of galled roots	Galls per root
Neem oil at 100ml/1 L of water	0.6	1.0
Neem oil at 100ML/2L of water	2.5	1.0
Neem oil at 100ML/3L of water	2.6	1.0
Worm Force at 20g/m ² (Positive control)	1.8	1.0
Negative Control	5.38	4.68
LSD (0.05)	1.09	1.2

The enhanced growth and yield parameters of the crop in the treated plots indicated that the neem seed oil provided a conducive and pest-free micro-environment for the thriving of the crop. Plants treated with Neem oil at 100 ml / 3 L consistently produced more and heavier fruits than other concentrations and the negative control. This concentration was milder on the crop than the higher concentrations. Kumar and Yadav (2020) found that neem oil sprays increased tomato fruit yield and reduced insect infestation, though differences were sometimes not significant due to environmental variability.

Neem extracts are known to deter common field pests and fungal infections. *Azadirachtin* acts as an antifeedant and growth regulator. Reduced pest pressure can indirectly enhance fruit set and weight. Higher dilution (100 ml / 3 L) likely reduced potential phytotoxic effects and allowed plants to allocate more resources to fruit development, whereas more concentrated treatments may have caused mild stress or reduced photosynthetic efficiency (Ebere *et al.*, 2018).

The results clearly demonstrated the nematicidal effects of the aqueous neem seed oil extract by significantly reducing the number of galled roots and galls per root, when compared with the untreated control. The significant reduction in galling suggests that neem oil extract could serve as a sustainable alternative to synthetic nematicides.

The highest neem oil concentration (100 ml/L) gave the best nematode suppression, suggesting effectiveness in reducing *Meloidogyne* (Root-knot nematode) infection. The inhibitory effect can be attributed to the nematicidal properties of neem compounds, such as *azadirachtin*, *nimbin*, and *salannin*, which interfere with nematode feeding and reproduction. Khan *et al.* (2021) reported that neem contains several biologically active compounds such as *azadirachtin*, *nimbin*, *salannin*, and *meliantrio*, which exhibit anti-feedant, growth-regulating, and sterilizing effects on nematodes. Similarly, Akhtar and Malik (2000) reported that neem seed cake and leaf extracts significantly reduced *Meloidogyne incognita* populations in tomato and okra.

The results also showed that concentrated dilution (100 ml / 1L) was more depressive than higher dilutions (100 ml / 2L or 3L). This could be due to the fact that extremely concentrated extracts may cause phytotoxic stress on roots, limiting absorption or damaging root tissues, thereby reducing overall plant resistance, as pointed out by research done by Ebere *et al.* (2018). Proper dilution likely allows the active compounds to remain biologically effective against nematodes while minimizing plant toxicity. The results reinforce neem's potential as a biological control agent against root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.), particularly when applied at optimal dilution levels. According to several

studies (Akhtar and Malik, 2000 and Adegbite and Adesiyani, 2011), neem suppresses nematodes through inhibition of egg hatching and larval penetration, reduced nematode reproduction rate, and induced systemic resistance (ISR) in plants, enhancing their natural defense mechanisms.

Okra has potential as an industrial crop and also has been tested in the developed world; its cultivation and use are second to none. Root-knot nematode is an economically important pathogen of tomatoes grown under open as well as protected cultivation. Considering the crops' high nutritive value and the export potential, successful cultivation in the country should be attempted by using 100 ml / 3 L of neem seed oil aqueous extract.

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